

D2.4 FINAL IMPACT REPORT ON SUPPORT FOR EU PARTICIPATION IN RDA

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Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition
CODATA	Committee on Data for Science and Technology
ECRs	Early Career Researchers
ESIP	Earth Science Information Partners
IG	Interest Group
NISO	National Information Standards Organisation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WDS	World Data Systems
WG	Working group

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines the work of the RDA EU project on the programmes designed to support the participation of individuals in RDA processes with a focus on the engagement in the RDA working meetings and workshops, activities of the Working and Interest groups and adoption, training, outreach and wider dissemination.

In particular, under the project's WP2 "Support to European participation in RDA processes", RDA Europe has developed and sustained three different platforms to engage and support the EU individual participation in RDA. The summary information and reference key performance indicators are illustrated in the table below:

Grant	Focus	Total Grants foreseen (M1-M27)	Total Grants awarded (M1-M30)	KPI reference and status upon project completion
Early Career Researchers (ECR)	support for early career data researchers to engage with RDA	28	33	KPI 2.2 - exceeded
Experts	support for data professionals to support RDA WG / IGs	20	28	KPI 2.1 - exceeded
Ambassadors	discipline-specific awareness raising and community engagement	12 + 2*	12 + 2*	KPI 2.3 - achieved

Table 1- Grant programmes breakdown in terms of focus, numbers and reference KPIs

**2 ambassadors are supported as part of the national node contract with The Netherlands / DANS*

Two of the programmes have had a particular focus on supporting participation in the RDA working meetings, the RDA Plenaries, and the work of the RDA groups, for two specific categories of RDA membership: **Experts and the Early Careers**.

The third programme developed, the one dedicated to the **RDA EU Ambassadors**, was aimed at supporting participation by engaging specific discipline communities and building a two-way communication channel streamlining RDA outputs and contributions to domain communities and ensuring their vice-versa input in terms of requirements and best practices into the RDA.

This document outlines the different support programmes, the results and aspects related to the impact of these in relation to the RDA Europe 4.0 objectives especially:

- Objective 2 – Providing the skilled, voluntary resources from the EU investment to address Digital Single Market (DSM) issues;
- Objective 3 – Facilitating cross-disciplinary & multi-disciplinary research;
- Objective 4 – Building, strengthening, and consolidating an RDA global community;
- Objective 5 – Contributing to global interoperable data infrastructure;
- Objective 6 – Democratising access to funding opportunities in data infrastructures & interoperability.

Additional information on the grants process, open calls and overall grants management is available in deliverable *D1.5 Cascading grants management* report while the details around the dissemination and promotional campaigns are included in deliverable *D5.5 Final Communication, Marketing & Stakeholders Engagement report*.

1. RDA EU Early Career Researcher programmes

The Early Career Researcher (ECR) programme supported through the RDA Europe 4.0 and previous projects, was initiated in 2014 and has become a platform to introduce early career researchers working with data to the RDA allowing them to share ideas, experiences and practical advice, while learning what leading data scientists and practitioners are currently working on.

This programme offered grant winners the opportunity to engage directly with and support the work of RDA Working and Interest Groups, to learn and contribute, and become a part of the RDA global data sharing community.

The programme aligned with both the European project objectives as well as the RDA global vision of engaging a diversified and inter-generational community, supporting a new generation of leadership and fostering their opportunity to obtain expertise regarding data infrastructure while becoming well-connected at an early stage in their career¹.

1.1. The RDA EU Early Careers

The Early Career profile as outlined in the calls encouraged diversity while focusing on the career and study requirements:

- Currently engaged in Bachelor, Masters, PhD or Postdoc studies - applicants must be enrolled in a higher education study course or within maximum 5 years after completing a PhD in the case of Postdoc studies;
- Studies are/were conducted in a higher education or research institution based in one of the EU Member states or Associated countries
- Studies are of relevance to RDA Recommendations or Outputs and cover at least one of the Working or Interest Groups.

Grantees were selected based on:

- Area of interest, relevance of their work to RDA activities and foreseen benefits (criterion weight 60%);
- Proficiency in English (good knowledge of English is required to generate written content) (criterion weight 20%);
- Understanding of the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR data movement; knowledge of the Open Science agenda, and how these intend to evolve in Europe (criterion weight 20%);

Furthermore the following criteria to establish balanced and diverse participation and distribution of grants:

- Geographical balance;
- Gender balance;
- Preference given to candidates who have not already previously received RDA funding;
- Preference given to candidates in underrepresented fields within RDA.

1.2. The ECR grantees and grant programme in numbers

During the RDA Europe 4.0 project lifetime, five editions of the grants programme were completed, all timed with the RDA bi-annual working meetings, the RDA Plenaries². The full list of grantees and additional details regarding their higher education institution affiliation, type of study or relevant work is

¹ <https://rd-alliance.org/get-involved/studentearly-career-programms>

² The five RDA Plenary associated with the ECR grants: 11th Plenary - March 2018, Berlin; 12th Plenary - Nov 2018, Gaborone; 13th Plenary - April 2019, Philadelphia; 14th Plenary - October 2019, Helsinki; 15th Plenary - March 2020, Virtual meeting / planned for Melbourne

available in Annex 1.

A total of 75 eligible applications were received and 33 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary	2	1	1 United Kingdom	1 Female
12 th Plenary	17	8	6 Austria, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia Slovenia, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Austria, Portugal	6 Female / 2 Male
13 th Plenary	19	7	6 Austria, France, Germany, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland	4 Female / 3 Male
14 th Plenary	21	10	8 Austria, Hungary, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom	5 Female / 5 Male
15 th Plenary	16	7	5 Croatia, Hungary, Germany, Romania (initial selection also included Estonia ³)	5 Female / 2 Male

Table 2 - ECR grants breakdown in terms of numbers, geographical coverage and gender balance

As mentioned in the section detailing the balance criteria, the grants committee has carefully looked into ensuring **good gender representation** and furthermore, the higher share of females in the EC grantees is **a hope to increase the fraction of RDA Female "Experts" in the future**. This also highlights the overall RDA long term commitment at enabling and promoting gender balance in addition to the geographical, professional and disciplinary one.

1.3. Support to RDA processes - bringing forward diverse disciplinary perspectives

The evaluation process has also aimed for a broad domain and RDA groups coverage. The candidates were assigned and introduced to RDA groups that matched as **best as possible the disciplinary background and research interests** of the candidates. The table below highlights the domain /disciplinary coverage.

<i>Grantees for the 11th Plenary – discipline coverage⁴</i>
Natural Sciences/Biological sciences
<i>Grantees for the 12th Plenary – discipline coverage</i>

³ Following the procedure outlined by the Grants committee, following 3 different consecutive cancellations the available grants offered to the candidates order on the reserve list to ensure all available grantee spots were covered

⁴ The Frascati Manual 2015 was used as a reference classification for both groups and grantees background, expertise and research interests https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/science-and-technology/frascati-manual-2015_9789264239012-en#page61

1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Engineering and Technology/Materials engineering 1 Humanities/History and archaeology 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences 2 Social Sciences/Other social sciences
<i>Grantees for the 13th Plenary - discipline coverage</i>
1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 3 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology
<i>Grantees for the 14th Plenary - discipline coverage</i>
2 Humanities/Other humanities 3 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 2 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Medical and Health Sciences/Health sciences 1 Agricultural Sciences/Animal and dairy science 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences
<i>Grantees for the 15th Plenary - discipline coverage</i>
1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Humanities/Other humanities 1 Humanities/Art (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music) 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Medical and Health Sciences/Basic medicine 1 Engineering and Technology/Industrial Biotechnology 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences -- Initially ⁵ 1 Social Sciences/Other social sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology

Table 3 - ECR grants disciplinary coverage

1.4. Support to RDA Working and Interest groups

All grantees were assigned and introduced to three Working and/or Interest groups to support: note taking, meeting summaries, on site logistics, assistance to meeting coordination and other activities agreed with the group co-chairs.

Below is a snapshot list of the groups that have involved Early Career grantees in their activities relative to each edition of the ECRs programme / each Plenary meeting:

⁵ 2 of the 3 candidates that withdrew but had been initially selected covered the different domains listed below

Grantees for the 11th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG

Grantees for the 12th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Disciplinary Collaboration Framework
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG Health Data / WG Blockchain Applications in Health
 IG Libraries for Research Data
 IG Metadata
 IG PID
 IG RDA/CODATA Legal Interoperability
 IG RDA/NISO Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets
 IG Repository Platforms for Research Data
 IG Reproducibility
 IG Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions
 IG Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC)
 WG BioSharing Registry
 WG Data Usage Metrics
 WG Data Versioning
 WG DMP Common Standards
 WG Empirical Humanities Metadata
 WG PID Kernel Information
 WG Provenance Patterns
 WG RDA/WDS Scholarly Link Exchange
 BoF FAIR Data and Open Science
 BoF GO FAIR

Grantees for the 13th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Active Data Management Plans
 IG Data Discovery Paradigms
 IG Data policy standardisation and implementation
 IG Disciplinary Collaboration Framework
 IG Domain Repositories
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data
 IG Libraries for Research Data
 IG Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC)
 IG Software Source Code
 WG Agrisemantics
 WG Data Citation
 WG Data Usage Metrics
 WG DMP Common Standards
 WG Exposing Data Management Plans
 WG FAIR Data Maturity Model
 BOF Coordinating Global Open Science Commons initiatives

Grantees for the 14th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Data Policy Standardisation and Implementation IG
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Education and Training on Handling of Research Data
 IG ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences
 IG Libraries for Research Data
 IG Open Science Graphs for FAIR Data
 IG PID
 IG RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories
 IG Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions
 IG Vocabulary Services
 WG Data Usage Metrics
 WG Data Versioning
 WG DMP Common Standards: Machine-actionable DMPs
 WG RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World
 WG Research Metadata Schemas
 BoF Building Dataverse Communities that follow RDA Best Practices for Data Sharing and Management
 BoF Repository Interfaces for Data Analytics (RIDA)

Grantees for the 15th Plenary – RDA WG & IG coverage

IG Active Data Management Plan
 IG Biodiversity Data Integration
 IG Early Career and Engagement
 IG Education and Training on Handling of Research Data
 IG Engaging Researchers With Research Data
 IG Health Data
 IG Social Dynamics of Data Interoperability
 IG Social Science Research Data
 WG DMP Common Standards
 WG Reproducible Health Data Services
 WG FAIR data Maturity Model
 BoF Challenges in Professionalizing Data Stewardship
 Joint meeting of the IG Data for Development
 IG Disciplinary Collaboration Framework
 IG ESIP/RDA Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences
 IG RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals

Table 4 - ECR grants coverage of RDA Working and Interest groups

In addition to the practical support for the group working meetings, Early Career grantees have made active contributions or have taken on active roles in groups working and have pursued specific aspects related to their research as highlighted below:

Florenzia Grattarola: Working on a large and multidisciplinary collaborative initiative to establish a model for a national system of quantification, management, storage and distribution diversity and conservation data while looking into aspects of education and research incentives as rewards.

Ana Slavec: Working on the development and implementation of the organisational data management

plan and assisting other researchers with data collection, analysis, and reporting. Values RDA as the place to address issues such as a lack of disciplinary repositories for the research areas such as renewable materials.

Yasemin Turkyilmaz-van der Velden: PhD candidate and one of the Data Stewards Delft University of Technology (the Netherlands), involved in the Education and Training on handling of research data IG and the Active Data Management Plans IG - both in light of her role at TU Delft.

Maja Dolinar: Works on a PhD research project on "Sustainability of Open Research Data for Marketing Research". At the same time she is Head of Digital Preservation at the Social Science Data Archives - ADP (Slovenia) working on open data policies, trustworthy data archive policies, and long-term data preservation management.

Rossella Aversa: Was particularly interested in Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions and Domain Repositories interest groups both matching work around building up a distributed repository for the nanoscience community within the NFFA-Europe project.

Dorothea Strecker: Has collected input from the joint groups meeting on "Shareable Data: Metadata, issues of Privacy and Legal implications" for her work on legal implications of sharing data and has outlined the group developments as positive steps towards implementing legal metadata in machine actionable DMPs and facilitating informed decision making based on metadata while addressing legal uncertainty.

Laura Rothfritz: Currently pursuing a Masters degree in Information Sciences at the Applied University Potsdam (Germany) working on quality criteria for research data (management), following closely the work of the WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG and the Active Data Management Plans Interest Group.

Martina Trognitz: Collected feedback on the steps she and her colleagues at the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities have adopted in establishing a digital long-term archive for research data from the humanities, as well as submitting it for certification - aspects related to FAIR, Certification, Data versioning and Usage metrics.

João Rocha: Became chair of the Repository Platforms for Research Data IG - currently building a repository solution for his institution and is seeking feedback on the choices made, plans to set up a WG (driven by the RPRD IG) as a forum for discussion and comparison of research data management platforms.

Romain David: Contributing to developing FAIR assessment grids and appropriate recommendations in the SHARC's IG and providing input in agriculture data related-groups as both closely connected to the work at INRA and related PhD project.

Kathleen Gregory: A PhD candidate working on open source search solutions for research data, is actively involved with the Data Discovery Paradigms IG, she is co-author on the best practices article published as an output from the IG.

Stephanie van de Sandt: Working on a PhD project related to Data Usage and Software Source Code identification, tracking reuse of research data and software in publications and contributing to CERN's research data information infrastructures, such as the CERN Open Data Portal. Actively involved among other with the Data Usage Metrics WG.

Tobias Weber: Particularly contributing to the Data Usage Metrics WG, complementing his research project on automatic quality assessment approaches, how well machines can assess the quality of research data compared to human experts.

Daniela Hausen: Enrolled in a MLIS focused on RDM for chemistry is actively participating in the

Chemistry Research Data IG, Sharing Rewards and Credits (SHARC) IG and Research Data Management in Engineering IG. Has actively worked on the Charter for the Research Data Management in Engineering IG.

Stefan Reichmann: Working on a PhD project on social & cultural aspects of Research Data Management, focusing on understand cultural preconceptions of research and publication practices in selected disciplines and address them to facilitate the introduction of local level support structures for Research Data Management and Open Science such as repository services and training for researchers as well as students.

Joana Rodrigues: Working to assist researchers from different domains to organize, describe and publish their datasets but particularly interested in the work of the Long Tail of Research Data IG and discipline focused approaches to data curation in the long tail.

1.5. Supporting inter-generational and cross disciplinary knowledge exchange

All grantees have been encouraged to join the [Early Career and Engagement Interest Group](#) and the wider Early Career and Fellows network inside the RDA and take advantage of the various support activities, including the Mentorship programme the group runs bringing together senior RDA members and researchers at the beginning of their career and newcomers to RDA.

In addition to the support provided the Working and Interest group meetings, grant winners have also actively taken part in the **Plenary poster sessions** displaying posters summarising their studies and areas of interest. This has provided grantees with an opportunity to speak to and share ideas with other RDA community members working on similar topics or disciplines, and learn from their experience.

Figure 1 - RDA EU Early Careers at RDA Plenary poster sessions

Upon completing their assignments, grantees provided a publishable summary of the Plenary, meetings and their experience and take-aways. The collected reports have been published as blogs on the RDA website <https://rd-alliance.org/blog>. The table below provides links and authorship information for blog reports:

Title	Author
RDA and the 15th RDA Plenary - views of an Early Career Researcher	Caterina Tomulescu
Attending P15. An early career perspective.	Frederic von Vlahovits
Participation at RDA 15th Plenary Virtual Meeting challenged by the world pandemic	Marta Balog
My experience with the VP15 - between Melbourne and Berlin	Katarzyna Biernacka
From the very beginning to VP15 - an experience report	Patrick Helling
Early career experience	Sarah Stryeck
Data (Stewardship) Makes the Difference: Towards a community-endorsed data stewardship profession.	Connie Clare
Trip report: RDA 14th plenary (Joao Moreira)	Joao Moreira
RDA Plenary 14th – A New And Exciting Experience for an Early Career	Alexander Götz
An overview of RDA 14th meeting as an early career grantee	Maria Tsagiopoulou
An Early Career Grantee take on the 14th RDA Plenary	João Manuel Cardoso
An early-career experience at the 14th RDA Plenary in Helsinki	Nuria Bautista
RDA 14th Plenary Meeting - RDA, The EU, EOSC and maDMPs	Simon Oblasser
RDA Fourteen Plenary: The Early Career Experience	Yulia Karimova
RDA P13 - Networking, IG Research Data Management in Engineering and DMP as an important topic	Daniela Hausen
RDA Thirteenth Plenary: The Early Career Experience	Joana Rodrigues
RDA 13: The Social and the Technical updated	Tobias Weber
Summary content of Agrisemantics WG (Breakout session RDA P13)	Romain David
A (not so) Early Career Researcher's Experience at the 13th RDA Plenary	Kathleen Gregory
Attending the RDA 13th Plenary Meeting "With data comes responsibility" as an Early Career Grantee	Stefan Reichmann
Experiencing the International Data Week 2018 in Gaborone	Maja Dolinar
Many precious first time experiences, thanks to RDA Europe Early Career Programme	Yasemin Turkyilmazvan der Velden
My first RDA plenary and the IDW2018 in Botswana	Ana Slavec
Addressing legal implications of sharing data	Dorothea Strecker

Title	Author
#IDW2018 at Botswana: These are exciting times to get into research data management	Joao Rocha
All is FAIR in love and data - attending the 12th RDA plenary in Botswana	Laura Rothfritz
Four days at the IDW18 in Gaborone	Rosella Aversa
The International Data Week 2018 and my first RDA Plenary	Martina Trognitz

Table 5 – ECR blog reports and testimonials

RDA 14th Plenary, 23-25 October 2019

Helsinki | Espoo
Finland
23-25 October 2019

^ RDA P14 Early Careers

 João Cardoso , INESC-ID Computer Science Read the Poster	
 Alexander Götz , Leibniz Supercomputing Centre Natural Sciences, Engineering and Technology Read the Blog Post Read the Poster	
 Péter Király , Göttingen eResearch Alliance Humanities/Other humanities Read the Poster	
 Simon Oblasser , Vienna University of Technology Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, Information engineering Read the Blog Post Read the Poster	
 Maria Tsaglopoulou , Institute of Applied Biosciences, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (INAB CERTH) Natural Sciences/Biological sciences, Medical and Health Sciences/Other medical sciences Read the Blog Post Read the Poster	

Figure 2 P14 ECRs and contributions as illustrated on the RDA Europe Grants platform

The figure 2 illustrates the RDA ECR grants page on the grants.rd-alliance.org platform and highlights the example of the grantees related to the RDA 14th Plenary held in Helsinki, October 2019.

2. RDA EU Expert programmes

The Experts grants programme was designed to support the active participation of European data professionals in a more advanced stage of their career with respect to ECRs. Detailed criteria for applicants included:

- Experts are broadly defined as mid-career or senior data professionals / scientists;
- Be involved in RDA as active member, participant, chair, or contributor to a WG or IG, especially in the past 12 to 18 months;
- Be proactive and willing to contribute to RDA Recommendations or Outputs testing and adoption activities in European institutions;
- Actively engage in Plenaries, national, and/or regional workshops and related initiatives;
- Have the ability to recruit collaborators across different segments of the European data community;
- Be part of an active data community and have a good understanding of the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; knowledge of the Open Science agenda, and how these intend to evolve in Europe;
- Reside/work in one of the EU Member states or Associated countries

Grantees were selected based on:

- A statement describing their interest in and commitment to the vision of RDA, in-progress Working/Interest Groups and/or one or more existing RDA Recommendations and Outputs; plans for future involvement and expected benefits (criterion weight 35%);
- A summary of previous and current activities demonstrating their involvement and contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest groups, development and /or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs in European Institutions (criterion weight 35%);
- Wider engagement with other initiatives and/or national activities (and the national RDA node, if applicable) belonging to the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; and/or initiatives on defining and implementing the Open Science agenda at national and European levels (criterion weight 30%);

While considering the following criteria to establish balanced and diverse distribution of the grants:

- Geographical balance;
- Gender balance;
- Preference to candidates that have not already previously received RDA funding;
- Preference to candidates in underrepresented fields within RDA.

2.1. The Expert grantees and grant programme in numbers

As in the case of the ECR Open Calls, 5 editions of the grants programme were completed, all timed with the RDA bi-annual working meetings (RDA Plenaries). A complete list of the Expert grantees including details on their affiliation and involvement with the RDA groups, is available in Annex 2.

A total of 63 eligible applications were received and 28 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process.

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
11 th Plenary	11	5	4 Austria, Finland, Greece, Spain	2 Female / 3 Male
12 th Plenary	12	5	2 Austria, United Kingdom	1 Female / 4 Male
13 th Plenary	10	6	5 Greece, France, Italy, Ireland, United Kingdom	2 Female / 4 Male
14 th Plenary	14	7	6 Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom	4 Female / 3 Male
15 th Plenary	16	5	5 Denmark, Finland, Germany, Italy, Ireland (initial selection also included Hungary)	2 Female / 4 Male

Table 6 - Expert grants breakdown in terms of numbers, geographical coverage and gender balance

The discipline coverage has also been diverse and aimed to bring forward under-represented domains

<i>Grantees for the 11th Plenary – discipline coverage</i>
1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Humanities/Other humanities 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology
<i>Grantees for the 12th Plenary – discipline coverage</i>
2 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Chemical sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences
<i>Grantees for the 13th Plenary – discipline coverage</i>
3 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Agricultural Sciences/Agricultural biotechnology 1 Medical and Health Sciences/Health sciences
<i>Grantees for the 14th Plenary - discipline coverage</i>

<p>2 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Agricultural Sciences/Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries 1 Social Sciences/Law 1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Social Sciences/Other social sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences</p>
<p><i>Grantees for the 15th Plenary - discipline coverage</i></p>
<p>2 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Social Sciences/Political Science 1 Humanities/History and archaeology 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences -- Initially 1 Natural Sciences/Mathematics</p>

Table 7 - Expert grants disciplinary coverage

The successful candidates, active contributors to RDA activities, were expected to provide a detailed report as part of the grant assignment. The collected reports published under the blog section of the RDA website covered various disciplinary and technical topics, giving an account of the group meetings attended as well as highlighting any adoption use cases (finalized or in progress) they are involved in, challenges and lessons learned.

Title	Author
Efforts and investments in training and education for research data management – impressions from the RDA 14th Plenary Meeting	Maria Johnsson
Helsinki, Notebooks and the CODATA-RDA schools	Hugh Shanahan
‘Data makes the difference’ RDA Plenary 14, 2019 Helsinki	Freya Van Den Boom
RDA P14 in Helsinki as a "young expert" from a Supercomputing Centre	Stephan Hachinger
FAIR Boundary Spanning: Reflections on RDM and Interdisciplinary Research	Yan Wang
Plenary and group meetings report	Enrique Wulff
Attending the RDA 13th Plenary as an Expert – From Production to Adoption	Sophie Aubin
A summary of the 13th RDA plenary in Philadelphia from the perspective of an expert grant awardee.	Mervyn O Luing
Make RDA fair again	Giuseppe Fiameni
Highlights from RDA P13 from Anne Cambon-Thomsen, thanks to an expert grant to attend	Anne Cambon Thomsen
Building standards in responsibility	Fotis Psomopoulos
The Joint Meeting of the Metadata Groups at the 13th RDA Plenary	Alex Ball

Title	Author
RDA connecting people (also at airports!)	Tomasz Miksa
The RDA 12th Plenary meeting in Gaborone: Insights for Training from Africa	Hugh Shanahan
Botswana... but that's landlocked!	Justin Buck
A Truly Awesome Meeting, IDW Botswana, November 2018	Fiona Murphy
Advancing Digital Frontiers of Crystallography, Chemistry and Research Data in Botswana	Jan Bruno
RDA 11th Plenary Berlin: Active DMP excitement	Jimmy Angelakos
From a "newbie" to an "expert" in less than two years - how to engage in the RDA activities?	Tomasz Miksa

Table 8 - Expert blog reports and testimonials

The Expert programme has been a successful means of supporting European drivers and chairs of the RDA Working and Interest groups. Annex 2 contains a full list of the grantees as well as their connections and roles within specific RDA groups. A considerable percentage of the candidates have leveraged the grants to support their work with the groups, organise breakout sessions and follow up on group activities within the timeframe of RDA Plenaries.

Furthermore, Expert grant winners were invited to and have signed up to support the **Mentorship programme coordinated by the RDA Early Career and Engagement Interest Group**. This way, the two grant programmes complement each other in the effort to foster inter-generational exchange between researchers at different career levels.

3. RDA EU Ambassadors programme

The RDA EU Ambassadors programme provided 12 grants targeting recognised domain experts and skilled communicators, serving as conduits between the RDA and the wider domain specific communities they belong to. By ensuring this two-way communication, the programme aimed to support awareness raising around the work and outputs of RDA and also help discipline experts grow their network and collaborate with like-minded people and organisations.

RDA Europe had committed to providing Ambassadors with:

- operational support for the Ambassadorial work,
- support for the coordination of individual and overall group work,
- official acknowledgement of the role,
- support to increase the impact of their work, professional growth and recognition.

3.1. The RDA EU Ambassadors

The profile as outlined in the programme Terms of reference:

- An RDA Europe Ambassador is a recognised domain expert and skilled communicator, serving as conduit between RDA and the wider domain specific communities to which the Ambassador belongs.
- The Ambassador takes part in RDA activities and is supported to facilitate a 2-way communication and engagement channel: talking to data practitioners and organisations about

the work of RDA to disseminate RDA information via informal and formal channels; and making sure input from domain/discipline specific community(-ies) is incorporated in the work of RDA and shapes its future agenda.

- The Ambassadors will make active contributions to defining and promoting what RDA has to offer to discipline-specific communities. The ambassadorial work is carried out according to a detailed work plan that demonstrates impact for the domain community as well as RDA. The work will be disseminated via discipline-specific and general RDA communication channels, including presentations, webinars, training sessions, surveys, articles and reports.
- The mandate as Ambassador starts upon the confirmed successful selection and appointment and will be supported for the full duration of the RDA Europe 4.0 project (ending 31 May 2020). Ideally the mandate extends beyond that.

Grants selection criteria:

- The candidate profile and a summary of previous and current activities as influencer or representative of a domain specific community, with particular attention to data-focused activities/achievements in the Open Science context (20%);
- Statement about how the candidate expertise and work with data and the data community in their discipline is aligned with the mission and goals of RDA (15%);
- A summary of previous and current activities demonstrating your involvement and contributions to RDA related activities, Working/Interest groups, development and /or promotion and/or adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs (15%);
- A work plan of activities to be performed as part of the Ambassador role detailing how these will impact not only the community practices but will also make a significant contribution in the context of RDA. Reference Key Performance Indicators should be provided for macro-activities supporting impact assessment (35%);
- Wider engagement with other initiatives and/or national activities (and the national RDA node, if applicable) belonging to the European Data Infrastructures landscape, including initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud; the FAIR movement; and/or initiatives on defining and implementing the Open Science agenda at national and European levels (15%);

The RDA Europe 4.0 project organised two open calls waves for the recruitment of Ambassadors:

- September - November 2018
- February - May 2019

Open calls in numbers

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance
1st wave	17	6	5 Denmark, France, Italy, Slovenia, United Kingdom	2 Female / 4 Male
2nd wave	10	6	6 France, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, United Kingdom	4 Female / 2 Male
Ambassadors supported by nodes*	-	2	1 Netherlands	1 Female / 1 Male

Table 9 - Ambassador grants breakdown in terms of numbers, geographical coverage and gender balance

**2 domain Ambassadors are supported through the network of RDA EU national nodes, specifically the Node from the Netherlands, coordinated by DANS as the organisation has the necessary*

mechanisms and expertise to ensure the roles are covered by skilled candidates.

Figure 3 - Selected Ambassadors and discipline coverage

To support coordination and outreach, dedicated pages on the RDA website were set up covering overall programme outputs and resources as well as the individual profiles of the RDA Europe Ambassadors, and contact form, as detailed in the table below:

1. RDA EU Ambassadors page - on https://rd-alliance.org/
2. Wouter Addink - Natural Sciences
3. Julien Barde - Marine Sciences / Fisheries
4. Ricarda Braukmann - Social Sciences
5. Anne Cambon-Thomsen - Health sciences and for research ethics
6. Caterina Caracciolo - Agricultural Sciences
7. Sébastien Denvil - Earth Sciences / Climate modelling
8. Rene van Horik - Humanities
9. Eva Méndez - Interdisciplinary Research
10. Ingvill Constanze Mochmann - Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
11. Fiona Murphy - RDA EU Ambassador Media and Communications
12. Fotis Psomopoulos - Bioinformatics
13. Ana Slavec - Engineering/ Renewable Materials
14. Nikola Vasiljevic - Engineering and Technology / Wind energy
15. Shaun de Witt - High energy physics/ Fusion
16. RDA EU Ambassadors - grant programme summary on https://grants.rd-alliance.org/
17. RDA EU Ambassadors - contact form

Table 10 - Profile and information webpages related to the Ambassadors programme

3.2. Programme outputs

Based on their work plans and diverse disciplinary approaches the Ambassadors have focused their work on a range of outputs and activities. The group has shared experiences via the coordination calls, providing updates on progress and sharing examples of the various resources and outputs of their Ambassadorial work.

The table below details different categories of outputs, resources and activities that consolidated the impact of their work in terms of dissemination and outreach, engagement across disciplinary networks, adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs, support for the work of RDA via the RDA WG and IG, training and knowledge sharing within their communities as well as across disciplines:

Value of RDA for... analysis and reports	e.g. RDA For The Social Sciences - Updated report and supporting dataset ; RDA for the Humanities ; "The assessment of RDA through the prism of wind energy community", hosted on Github as a Live document: https://github.com/niva83/RDA-assessment
Discipline pages	e.g. RDA for Scholarly Communication , RDA for Social Sciences ;
Tailored Value of RDA for specific communities	e.g. What can RDA do for engineering? ; What is the Research Data Alliance and what will it do for you? (Presentation focused on the RDA added value for the wind energy community)
Training	e.g. ELIXIR / CODATA-RDA Research Data Science Advanced Workshop on Bioinformatics - Course materials ; Research Data Management For Renewable Materials And Products ; FAIR Data in the Scholarly Communications Life Cycle
Tools	e.g. Built an example of virtual research infrastructures for wind energy community, using binder ; CWL and Docker: automating workflows in Life Sciences ; refining R codes to facilitate FAIR data management of spatial data infrastructures from R (using geoflow R package);
Webinars	e.g. RDA For The Social Sciences And Humanities - Insights From The RDA Europe Domain Ambassadors , Activities and Results of the RDA COVID-19 Working Group ; Serving Statistical Classifications on the

	<u>Web</u>
Setting up/ Driving RDA groups	e.g. <u>launching the RDA for the Sustainable Development Goals Interest Group</u> ; <u>revision of the Biodiversity Data IG charter</u> ;
Contributions to RDA working meetings	e.g. <u>RDA for SDGs at the RDA 14th Plenary</u> ; <u>39 Hints to Facilitate the Use of Semantics for Data on Agriculture the Nutrition, Eleven quick tips and User requirements and recommendations</u> at RDA Adoption Week 2020
Workshops (co-organising)	e.g. <u>STM and the Center for Open Science on the Research Data Seminar</u> ; <u>Workshop On Research Data Management For Renewable Materials And Products</u>
Adoption	e.g. <u>FAO Adoption story</u> , <u>STM's Year of Research Data</u> - instructions on implementing SCHOLIX and other resources, <u>Adoption case for PIDINST WG</u> at DTU, <u>DiSSCo stand at Biodiversity_Next</u> with demonstrator of RDA/TDWG implementation
Video testimonials	e.g. <u>Interview with Anne Cambon-Thomsen</u> ; <u>interview with Ingvill Constanze Mochmann</u> ; <u>Interview with Fotis E. Psomopoulos</u>
Contributions at national level	e.g. <u>Interdisciplinary Research and the Future of Open Science in Spain</u> ; <u>RDA and the marine domain - RDA France</u> ; <u>RDA Italy- National workshop focusing on Agricultural data</u> , <u>PID NL - A workshop on the use of Persistent Identifiers in the Netherlands</u> .
Interviews & articles	e.g. <u>Open research and data sharing: Are we hearing what researchers are telling us?</u> , <u>In Finland as an RDA Europe Ambassador for Engineering/Renewable Materials</u> ; <u>Samen voor Open Science - edata and research magazine</u>
Outreach via disciplinary networks	e.g. <u>International data sharing and data integration through RDA</u> - at the GBIF Global Nodes Meeting; <u>STM's Year of Research Data</u> - on RDA/STM Joint Letter of Intent, RDA outputs on data policy and FAIR Data; <u>RDA opportunities for the Humanities and the DARIAH community</u>
Liaison Expert groups / connected project and initiatives	e.g. Ingvill Mochmann - member of OECD EG "Digital skills for data-intensive science", Eva Mendez as chair of the European Open Science Policy Platform, Fotis PSomopoulos - member of the EOSC Skill and Training WG, Several working with the EOSC related projects FAIRsFAIR, EOSC-hub, FREYA, FAIR4Health
RDA COVID-19 WG	e.g. Anne Cambon-Thomsen as WG Co-chair, Fotis E. Psomopoulos and Eva Mendez as sub-group moderators, Ingvill Mochmann as key contributor
Papers	e.g. <u>Data Discovery Paradigms: User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories</u> , DiSSCo and RDA adoption paper CODATA Data Science Journal
Connecting with Early Careers	e.g. Fotis E. Psomopoulos co-chair of the RDA Early Career and Engagement IG, Eva Mendez as co-chair of the Young European Research Universities Network YERUN Open Science Working Group, Ana Slavec as co-coordinator of the Open Science work group at The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc)

Table 11 - Ambassador programme references for outputs and resources

4. Lessons learnt

4.1. Early Career and Experts Grants – survey

Following the grant programmes, the project ran surveys to collect feedback from the grantees aiming to improve various aspects of the upcoming editions. A total of 16 grantees have provided input as both overall rating (as illustrated below) or as open text suggestions.

	EXCELLENT	GOOD	AVERAGE	POOR	VERY POOR
Communication on the grant programme	7	7	2	0	0
Information and instructions on the grant	10	5	1	0	0
Support in organising Plenary attendance	9	5	2	0	0
Your experience with the groups you have been assigned to / have worked with	11	3	0	2	0
Processes for reimbursing travel costs	4	6	6	0	0
Overall experience with the grant programme	11	5	0	0	0

Figure 4 - Sample of collected feedback

Grantees were encouraged to give feedback to improve their experience, and we have incorporated, among others, these very good examples:

- ECRs introductory / coordination virtual meeting prior to the Plenary meeting
- Dedicated meeting for grantees - formal and informal
- Anticipate the call timing as much as possible to give more time for travel planning
- Pins / Badges to indicate / recognised grantees during the meeting
- Support networking sessions to help connect ECRs and seasoned researchers

Based on feedback from the grantees, the external evaluators as well as the wider community, the Grants Committee has worked on continuously improving the support programmes in terms of the clarity of requirements and criteria, application process, FAQs and online support, evaluation process, grantees support and coordination activities.

Furthermore, the Grants Committee has monitored aspects related to discipline and WG and IG coverage and worked on engaging underrepresented communities and disciplines in order to provide a balanced distribution of funds and improved representation. Statistics on coverage were collected and new iterations of the grant programmes have been aimed at addressing the gaps.

4.2. Widening inclusion and focus

The mid-term project review report encouraged the project amend the criteria for future cascading grants to take into account varying degrees of existing engagement with open science practice and the degree of maturity of open science policies in different EU member states, with a view to favouring applications coming from countries where engagement was historically lower or where open science policies were less developed. For the cascading grants covered by this report, the primary influence was on the final calls for ECR and Expert grants where we made additional efforts to publicise the calls amongst the EU13 countries and, where relevant, amended evaluation criteria to favour participation from such countries.

In addition, the evaluation criteria for all calls (as described above) favoured participants engaged in domains of research that were otherwise under-represented or had not previously received funding. The tables in sections 1, 2 and 3 above demonstrate that this was successful, allowing a wider range of disciplines within Europe to benefit from the work of RDA.

4.3. Report on the Ambassadors programme

Based on a series of interviews with the Ambassadors, exchanges during the coordination calls as well as observations on the overall initiative, Francoise Genova, co-chair of the Ambassadors programme has provided a report bringing forward a series of considerations of value to the RDA EU 4.0 project and RDA global, and any similar programmes that would be run under the umbrella of the latter.

The report provides an overview of different aspects of the Ambassadorial work looking at motivations, approaches and work plans, identifying a set of common themes but also highlighting the fact that the approach had to be customized for each community, and the challenges faced by the Ambassadors. It looks at the work performed within the various communities, the work within the RDA, dissemination and collaboration with the national nodes, and exceptional contributions to the work RDA has done in terms of recommendations and guidelines for data sharing in the COVID-19 context. In terms of challenges, the report discusses in particular the difficulties of driving cultural change while shining a spotlight on the various types of outputs and resources produced. Messages from the Ambassadors to the RDA are also gathered. In closing, a set of conclusions are provided regarding the Ambassador role in general and the value of such a programme for both the Ambassadors themselves as well as for organisations running it, in this case the RDA and the RDA Europe project, as well as practical recommendations for similar programmes which may be set up.

5. Annexes

Annex 1 - Complete list of Early Career programme grantees

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Higher education Affiliation	Type of Study
11th Plenary	Florença	Grattarola	United Kingdom	University of Lincoln	PhD in Life Sciences
12th Plenary	Rossella	Aversa	Italy	CNR-IOM Istituto di Officina dei Materiali	Post-Doctoral researcher
12th Plenary	Maja	Dolar	Slovenia	University of Ljubljana	PhD in Business Studies
12th Plenary	João	Rocha	Portugal	INESC TEC - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores	Post-Doctoral researcher
12th Plenary	Laura	Rothfritz	Germany	University of Applied Sciences, Potsdam	Masters in Information Sciences
12th Plenary	Ana	Slavec	Slovenia	InnoRenew CoE	Post-Doctoral researcher
12th Plenary	Dorothea	Strecker	Germany	Humboldt University	Masters in Information Sciences
12th Plenary	Martina	Trognitz	Austria	University of Heidelberg, Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities	PhD in Classical Archaeology
12th Plenary	Yasemin	Turkyilmaz-van der Velden	The Netherlands	Erasmus University Medical Center, Rotterdam	PhD in Molecular Biology and Genetics
13th Plenary	Romain	David	France	National Institute for Agronomic Research	PhD in Environmental Information Systems
13th Plenary	Kathleen	Gregory	The Netherlands	DANS/Maastricht University	PhD in Science & Technology Studies
13th Plenary	Daniela	Hausen	Germany	University of Applied Sciences Cologne	Masters in Library and Information Science
13th Plenary	Stefan	Reichmann	Austria	Graz University of Technology	PhD in the Social Sciences
13th Plenary	Joana	Rodrigues	Portugal	INESC TEC - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores	PhD in Digital Media

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Higher education Affiliation	Type of Study
13th Plenary	Stephanie	van de Sandt	Switzerland	CERN	PhD in Library and Information Science
13th Plenary	Tobias	Weber	Germany	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre	PhD in Computer Science
14th Plenary	Nuria	Bautista	Spain	University Carlos III of Madrid	Ph.D. candidate at the Research Institute for Higher Education and Science
14th Plenary	João Manuel	Cardoso	Portugal	INESC-ID - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores	Junior researcher Information & decision support systems / MSc Telecommunications & Informatics Engineering
14th Plenary	Alexander	Götz	Germany	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre	Research Engineer at Leibniz Supercomputing Centre / PhD TU Munich
14th Plenary	Yulia	Karimova	Portugal	FEUP/ INESC TEC - INESC TEC - Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores	Researcher /PhD Student in Digital Media
14th Plenary	Péter	Király	Hungary / Germany	University of Göttingen, Faculty of Humanities	PhD in comparative literature and cultural studies
14th Plenary	Joao	Moreira	The Netherlands	University of Twente and VU Amsterdam	Post - doctoral researcher
14th Plenary	Simon	Oblasser	Austria	Vienna University of Technology	M.S. in Software Engineering & Internet Computing
14th Plenary	Sarah	Stryeck	Austria	Graz University of Technology	Postdoctoral Researcher at Institute for Interactive Systems and Data Science
14th Plenary	Maria	Tsagiopoulou	Greece	Institute of Applied Biosciences at the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	PhD in Biology/Bioinformatics
14th Plenary	Connie	Clare	United Kingdom	University of Nottingham	PhD student in Developmental Biology and Epigenetics

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Higher education Affiliation	Type of Study
15th Plenary	Muhammed ⁶	Abdulai	Estonia	School of Governance, Law and Society, Tallinn University	PhD student in Internationalization of Higher Education
15th Plenary	Marta	Balog	Croatia	Faculty of Medicine, J. J. Strossmayer University of Osijek	Postdoctoral researcher - depart. Medical Biology and Genetics, Laboratory for Neurobiology
15th Plenary	Katarzyna	Biernacka	Germany	Humboldt University	PhD studies Legal Barriers to Publication of Research Data
15th Plenary	Patrick	Helling	Germany	University of Cologne, Data Center for the Humanities (DCH)	Researcher and PhD Student at the Institute for Digital Humanities
15th Plenary	Anastasia	Kvasza	Hungary	Central European University	PhD in Environmental Sciences and Policy
15th Plenary	Iva ⁷	Melinščak Zlodi	Croatia	University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences	PhD Social Sciences / Information and Communication Sciences
15th Plenary	Urianni	Merlin	Croatia	University of Pula	PhD Pedagogy / Early learning
15th Plenary	Caterina	Tomulescu	Romania	University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine	PhD Biotechnology
15th Plenary	Frederic	von Vlahovits	Germany	Academy of Sciences and Literature / Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz	Research Associate and PhD Student Digital Humanities /Art

Annex 2 - Complete list of Expert programme grantees

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Affiliation	Working with the RDA groups
11th Plenary	Jimmy	Angelakos	United Kingdom	EDINA, University of Edinburgh	Exposing Data Management Plans WG DMP Common Standards WG FAIRSharing Registry: connecting data policies, standards & databases WG
11th Plenary	Heidi	Laine	Finland	University of Helsinki / Finnish Council of University Rectors UNIFI	Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG Empirical Humanities Metadata Working Group Exposing Data Management Plans WG

⁶ Candidate initially selected for the grant but withdrawn due to the COVID-19 organisational and international travel restrictions

⁷ Candidate initially selected for the grant but withdrawn due to the COVID-19 organisational and international travel restrictions

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Affiliation	Working with the RDA groups
11th Plenary	Eva	Méndez	Spain	Universidad Carlos III of Madrid	Repository Platforms for Research Data IG Libraries for Research Data IG Education and Training on handling of research data IG National Data Services IG
11th Plenary	Tomasz	Miksa	Austria	SBA Research	(Co-Chair)DMP Common Standards WG Data Security and Trust WG Data Citation WG Exposing Data Management Plans WG
11th Plenary	Fotis	Psomopoulos	Greece	Institute of Applied Biosciences (INAB CERTH)	(Co-chair) Data Discovery Paradigms IG (Co-chair) Early Career and Engagement IG Software Source Code Identification WG
12th Plenary	Ian	Bruno	United Kingdom	Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre	(Co-chair) Chemistry Research Data IG (Co-chair) Data Usage Metrics WG WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG
12th Plenary	Justin	Buck	United Kingdom	British Oceanographic Data Centre	Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems' Data IG Persistent Identification of Instruments WG
12th Plenary	Caterina	Caracciolo	Italy	Food and Agriculture Organization of the UN	(Co-chair) Agrisemantics WG Agricultural Data Interest Group (IGAD) Vocabulary Services IG Wheat Data Interoperability WG
12th Plenary	Tomasz	Miksa	Austria	Vienna University of Technology	(Co-Chair)DMP Common Standards WG Data Security and Trust WG Data Citation WG Exposing Data Management Plans WG
12th Plenary	Fiona	Murphy	United Kingdom	Murphy Mitchell Consulting Ltd	(Co-chair) Exposing Data Management Plans WG (Co-chair) RDA/WDS Publishing Data Workflows WG Data policy standardisation and implementation IG Mapping the Landscape IG
12th Plenary	Hugh	Shanahan	United Kingdom	Royal Holloway, University of London	(Co-chair) RDA/CODATA Summer Schools in Data Science and Cloud Computing in the Developing World WG (Co-chair) CODATA/RDA Research Data Science Schools for Low and Middle Income Countries IG (Co-chair) Development of cloud computing capacity and education in developing world research IG

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Affiliation	Working with the RDA groups
13th Plenary	Sophie	Aubin	France	Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique	(Co-chair) Agrisemantics WG Rice Data Interoperability WG Agricultural Data Interest Group (IGAD) Vocabulary Services IG
13th Plenary	Alex	Ball	United Kingdom	University of Bath	(Co-chair) Metadata IG (Co-chair) Metadata Standards Catalog WG Data in Context IG Libraries for Research Data IG
13th Plenary	Anne	Cambon-Thomsen	France	CNRS - French National Centre for Scientific Research CINECA	(Co-chair) Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG Ethics and Social Aspects of Data IG
13th Plenary	Giuseppe	Fiameni	Italy		Data Fabric IG Federated Identity Management IG Preservation e-Infrastructure IG
13th Plenary	Mervyn	O Luing	Ireland	Insight Centre for Data Analytics	Storage Service Definitions WG Array Database Assessment WG
13th Plenary	Fotis	Psomopoulos	Greece	Center for Research and Technology Hellas	(Co-chair) Data Discovery Paradigms IG (Co-chair) Early Career and Engagement IG Software Source Code Identification WG
14th Plenary	Stephan	Hachinger	Germany	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre	Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG PID IG
14th Plenary	Maria	Johnsson	Sweden	Lund University	Data Usage Metrics WG PID IG Education and Training on handling of research data IG
14th Plenary	Dimitra	Mavraki	Greece	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research	Metadata Standards Directory IG, FAIRsharing WG
14th Plenary	Hugh	Shanahan	United Kingdom	Royal Holloway, University of London	(Co-chair) CODATA-RDA schools in Research Data Science IG BoF on Computational Notebooks
14th Plenary	Freya	Van Den Boom	Netherlands	Bournemouth University	(co-chair) Teaching TDM on Education and Skill Development WG RDA/NISO Privacy Implications of Research Data Sets IG Data Security and Trust WG
14th Plenary	Yan	Wang	Netherlands	Delft University of Technology	Libraries for Research Data IG, Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG Engaging Researchers with Data IG

Ref.	Name	Surname	Country	Affiliation	Working with the RDA groups
14th Plenary	Enrique	Wulff	Spain	CSIC	RDA-CODATA Legal Interoperability of Research Data IG Fisheries Data Interoperability WG
15th Plenary	Leyla Jael	Garcia Castro	Germany	ZB MED Information centre for life sciences	Data Discovery Paradigms IG Research Metadata Schemas WG FAIR Data Maturity Model WG
15th Plenary	Edwin	Morley Fletcher	Italy	Lynkeus	(co-chair) Health Data IG Blockchain Applications in Health WG
15th Plenary	James	Savage	Ireland	University College Cork	(Co-chair) Libraries for Research Data IG Physical Samples and Collections in the Research Data Ecosystem IG Empirical Humanities WG
15th Plenary	Adela	Sobotkova	Denmark	Aarhus University	
15th Plenary	Andras	Telcs	Hungary	WIGNER RCP	Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions IG Repository Platforms for Research Data IG
15th Plenary	Ville	Tenhunen	Finland	University of Helsinki / IT	(co-chair) Repository Interfaces for Data Analytics (RIDA) WG National Data Services IG